

FACTORS FOR ENHANCING LITERACY

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Abstract. *The given article presents information about Uzbek language, the implementation of the law “On the State Language”, shortcomings in this regard, literacy issues, improving students’ literacy, research conducted in this regard, the role of the family in increasing students’ literacy. The impact of literacy, future challenges related to quality mother tongue instruction, increased attention to the issue of literacy, as well as issues related to the preparation of highly qualified personnel in this field will be covered.*

Keywords: *attention to Uzbek language, the law “On the State Language”, defects committed, literacy problems, improving students’ literacy, research conducted, family influence, future tasks, training of highly qualified personnel.*

Introduction. As a result of such important socio-political events as the independence of Uzbekistan and the legalization of Uzbek language as the state language, great changes are taking place in attitudes towards education. For our independent republic, the education of youth becomes even more important in a situation where it is important to prepare an entrepreneur, a creative and at the same time literate person.

Giving Uzbek language the status of a state language is a great event in the life of our country and people. The dreams of our ancestors have come true. Thanks to the Law “On the State Language” and independence, the prestige of Uzbek language was restored, and wide horizons were opened for its development. The native language is widely used in our republic not only as a means of communication, but also as a scientific, artistic and official language. The study, reading and teaching of Uzbek language, the publication of scientific and artistic works, and educational literature in Uzbek language are widely carried out. Our native language has become one of the sacred symbols of our independent state, which is protected by law and stands among the flag, coat of arms, anthem and Constitution. But there are issues that need to be addressed, deficiencies and youth literacy that are becoming relevant.

Literature analysis. Today, Uzbek language is actively used in all spheres of our life - state and public administration, interstate relations, science, education, medicine, culture and art, and is also heard on international platforms[1]. For the first time in the history of Uzbekistan, an Uzbek word was heard at the UN podium. This situation also shows the need to teach Uzbek language, that is, the state language, in educational institutions at the level of today's demand.

There were studied and analyzed manuals, programs and textbooks on language teaching methods from the point of view of the need to develop students' oral and written speech. For example, in the textbook “Studying the syntax of simple sentences at school” [2] by the methodist M. Omilkhanova, it is assumed that the study of grammatical material will contribute to the development of students’ speech and increase their literacy. In the work of methodologist A. Gulomov, “Activation of students’ cognitive activity in the process of teaching their native language” [3], the need to study language units with linguistic interpretation and their methodological use is determined. Methodologist M. Sobirova in a number of scientific works

[4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12] tries to substantiate the fact that the issue of literacy depends on a number of factors. One of the researchers, Kh. Gurbanova [13], thinks about the linguistic and methodological foundations for updating the content of the native language education, and A. Khamroev [14] in his monograph focuses on literacy based on projecting the creative activity of students into education in their native language. N. Murodova [15] discusses pronunciation and spelling errors in students' speech caused by the local dialect, and ways to correct them. Researcher G. Isakova [16,17,18] focuses her scientific research on solving literacy problems.

Research methodology. The article focuses on Uzbek language, the implementation of the law “On the State Language”, shortcomings in this regard, literacy issues, improving the literacy of students, research conducted in this direction, supporting families in improving literacy, and secret tasks for the future. Issues related to high-quality teaching of the native language, increased attention to the issue of literacy, as well as issues related to the training of highly qualified personnel in this area will be covered.

Analysis and results. Observations, experience of our work and analysis show that today in education, especially in language education, fundamental reforms are being implemented, large-scale work is being carried out to find and implement the most optimal and new ways to achieve the main goal of education. Based on the creation of a legal basis for Uzbek language to increase the status of the national language, stabilize attitudes towards the language, pay attention to the language, further stabilize feelings of respect for the language, create recognition of the “state language” in the minds of citizens of Uzbekistan, as well as issues of following it were put on the agenda day. Attitudes towards the state language and adherence to it have acquired social and political significance. The social function of Uzbek language has expanded.

Implementation of the Law “On the State Language” in government and government bodies; accounting, financial documentation, court cases at enterprises, institutions, organizations, public associations; notarial actions, conducting work in civil registration organizations in the state language, holding international scientific and practical conferences held in Uzbekistan in the state language, documents confirming a person and his rights, statements, proposals and complaints are drawn up in the state language.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to increase the prestige and status of Uzbek language as the state language” was promulgated. The “State Language Development Department” and “Thermal Commission” were created. A concept and road map for the development of the state language have been developed.

Television and radio broadcasts, publishing activities, postal and telegraph mailings, seals, stamps, texts of working documents, signs, advertisements, price lists, product labels, administrative-territorial units of the republic, districts, names of streets and geographical objects, texts of international treaties were planned of the Republic of Uzbekistan, mainly in the state language, and a number of works have been carried out in this direction.

There were achieved a number of successes in implementing the Law “On the State Language”. But there are things that need to be done and mistakes that are made. The defects remaining from Soviet times - erasing education, hiding students' unsatisfactory knowledge, raising grades, limiting democracy in schools - require updating the content of education. Reasonable opinions expressed by experts and workers of spiritual and educational organizations in the media, on radio, television, at scientific and practical conferences that the implementation of state language standards is not at the proper level, the system of working in the state language

is not respected. In addition to spelling and stylistic errors in the texts of advertisements and advertising on the streets, problems such as an increase in the number of foreign language texts and names await solutions.

During the research, we found out that students do not have enough skills and qualifications to distinguish linguistic phenomena and choose words suitable for the purpose of speech. According to our observations, many students encountered difficulties when asked to explain themselves due to the fact that they simply memorized linguistic rules and definitions without understanding their meaning.

We began our work to improve students' literacy by identifying errors and shortcomings in their oral and written speech.

At this point, we supported the opinion of the above scientists and intended to substantiate the great influence of the family in improving students' literacy.

It is known that the family, which is the basis of society, is the main place for formation of personality in all its aspects. Although all family members are considered to be educators to some extent, but it is the mother's unique education, most women today prefer to engage in trade rather than reading books and expand their knowledge. A child growing up in such conditions develops negative spiritual defects. Therefore, it is necessary to expand the worldview of mothers and create the opportunity to increase their knowledge in order to increase the spirituality of the child.

Considering that the healthy and spiritually mature development of youth depends on the situation in the family, the UN's declaration of the year as the "International Year of the Family" is aimed at increasing family attention to education.

Usually the child spends most of his time with the family. The behavior of his parents, their interest in his studies, their questions about his grades, their attempts to find out what homework he has, will certainly influence him. At this point, the child may ask them for help with homework, for example, because he was unable to complete it in his native language in accordance with the practice condition. Attempts by family members to help him at such a time, firstly, increase the child's sense of responsibility for completing the task, and secondly, evoke feelings of kindness towards the helpers. In conversations with parents, we sometimes hear the following statements: "My child is in 5th grade, and I'm also a 5th grader, doing my homework." Or it is said: "According to home exercise, replace "X" and "N", distinguish between "-ni" and "-ning". "I don't remember," I said, "do your job." In our opinion, in the first case, parents abuse their responsibilities for doing homework, and in the second, they lower their reputation in front of the child. The child loses interest in completing tasks.

The following endings occur during school life:

"When my daughter was in elementary school, I asked her about her homework every day and helped her when she had problems. I even solved some problems. I think the reason for this is that there are many subjects taught and teachers of different levels teach. In addition, due to increased family concerns, we did not have time to take an interest in his studies and monitor how he does his homework. Having moved to a higher class, he lost confidence in his own abilities. He doesn't want to continue his studies when he reaches 10th grade. Of course, we are also to blame for this situation." (From an interview with the mother of former student S.)

"We felt that when he started high school, he was ready for any subject he was going to answer, so we tried to encourage him to overcome his academic difficulties and encouraged him

to be active. Sometimes it happens like this. As soon as I got tired of work, he asked me to help me complete the task. At such a moment, I carefully explained my situation. Sometimes he didn't even want to complete an assignment in a subject that didn't interest him. Then I would patiently explain with examples that this science is also necessary in life. His hard work was combined with our demands in the family. He is now studying at a prestigious university in England.” (From a conversation with Mokhirakhan Mirzaeva)

When we surveyed children about their family situation, 40% of 100 schoolchildren said that the conditions in the family are good for extracurricular activities, parents always support them in completing their assignments, and 25% of schoolchildren say that parents try to help, but often said that at school it is known that mathematical problems solved with their help are incorrect or performed differently than in the case of exercises in their native language. 35 percent of students said that their parents do not help at all and do not even create conditions for preparing lessons.

Cases like these show that parents need to educate themselves and feel responsible for raising their children. We also distributed questionnaires to parents to determine their attitude to the influence of the family on improving the student's literacy.

1. What are the conditions for improving your child's literacy in the family. (For example, class, textbooks, dictionaries, teaching aids)
2. Are you interested in his studies?
3. What homework and assignments were given?
4. Will you help complete the assigned tasks?
5. What do you think prevents them from doing this? (Lack of knowledge, lack of time, lack of diligence)

The children's feedback did not coincide with the answers in the parents' questionnaires. This situation shows the indifference of many parents to raising their children. However, the cultural level and responsibility of parents are important in developing the student's spirituality and increasing the level of knowledge.

In our opinion, improving student literacy:

- analyze what family education was like in the past, what it was like under Soviet rule, what needs to be paid attention to in the current situation;
- do not neglect the family in improving students' literacy, taking into account its importance, increasing its responsibility and influence.

Solving the problems of strengthening the interaction of parents with the class teacher and subject teachers are pressing issues that develop the influence of the family.

The modern Uzbek literary language is a developed national language with a high social status, a refined phonetic and lexical-grammatical standard. It should be recognized that there are specific difficulties in determining lexical norms in the context of the multi-dialect of Uzbek language. Representatives of each dialect feel a barrier to using the variant of a word that naturally expresses a certain concept in their dialect. Naturally, the social environment influences the process of language use. People unknowingly or carelessly use other linguistic elements in their speech. Similar situations arise in the process of living together with representatives of other nationalities, working, getting an education, in a word, communicating with each other.

In the modern rapidly changing period of globalization, an in-depth study of issues related to the unique features of Uzbek language and literature, historical development, its current state

and prospects, strengthening the effectiveness of research activities carried out in this regard is the requirement of the time to radically improve the quality of teaching Uzbek language and literature at all levels of the education system, as well as the training of highly qualified and competent personnel in this area. Today, the tasks associated with the development of the native language and literature and their teaching are as follows:

- Training of highly qualified scientific and pedagogical personnel who thoroughly master the science of the state (Uzbek) language, its specific features, scientific, theoretical, philosophical and aesthetic foundations, modern educational technologies and meeting the requirements of the time;

- training of translators who, with high quality and skill, translate scientific, artistic and other literature from Uzbek language into English and other foreign languages, as well as from world languages into our native language;

- using the rich possibilities of Uzbek language and literature, to educate young people into spiritually mature people with a broad outlook and independent thinking, in the spirit of love and loyalty to the Motherland, respect for universal human values;

- creation of excellent scientific and educational literature that fully reflects the originality and characteristics of Uzbek language, its system of sounds and their reflection in writing, preparation of scientifically based proposals for improving the current spelling rules, various topics and directions, creation of dictionaries. and encyclopedias, brochures and textbooks;

- conducting scientific research on new and effective methods of teaching Uzbek language and literature in secondary schools, academic lyceums and vocational colleges, higher educational institutions, widespread introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies;

- ensuring a worthy place for Uzbek language in the global information network Internet, its computer style, scientific research related to the creation of translation programs and dictionaries, electronic textbooks based on Uzbek language and the world's leading methodological developments in foreign languages, preparation of practical recommendations and widespread implementation of what has been achieved in results in this regard.

In the republic, special attention is paid to the study of foreign languages, including English and Russian. Of course, learning a language gives you the opportunity to get acquainted with cultures and enriches your worldview. But this process should not be carried out at the expense of ignoring the issue of mother tongue and literacy. Zullisonain scientist Behbudi calls for learning not two, but four languages, but when studying a foreign language, Zinhar does not mean forgetting the native language - he considers the native language to be the basis of thinking.

In the process of general education, it is necessary to pay special attention to literacy, the study of the native language and literature, and the formation of language skills and competencies. Current issues are updating the system of teaching Uzbek language based on our national pedagogy, based on foreign experience, creating literature that meets the requirements of the time, and using innovative technologies. It is very important to develop in schoolchildren and students' language, speech, professional, communication, information reception, self-development, and the ability to express thoughts in accordance with the speech situation.

Language is the main factor determining the existence of a nation. On a global scale, some languages are falling out of use, and a global problem arises of preserving the native language. Our people's attitude towards the national language must change.

In our opinion, in the modern rapidly changing period of globalization, it is necessary to deeply study issues related to the unique features of Uzbek language and literature, its historical development, current state and prospects, as well as to strengthen the effectiveness of scientific activity, and research activities carried out in this direction are aimed at increasing attention to the issue of quality teaching of Uzbek language and literature at all levels of the education system, as well as the training of highly qualified personnel in this area and the developed program. According to it:

- in the course of in-depth study of historically established literary, linguistic schools and teachings of Uzbek language, literature and folklore, priceless monuments of the artistic thought of our great ancestors, students will be accustomed to independence and independent thinking, have a broad worldview in the spirit of love and loyalty to the Motherland, respect for universal human values, create fundamental scientific research, which is the basis for educating people as spiritually mature people;

- history of Uzbek language, the role of the language of the Bactrians, Sogdians, Khorezmians and other peoples and nationalities who lived on the territory of our country before the birth of Christ and in the first centuries of our era in the development of Uzbek language, the language of written monuments of the ancient Turkic language, comparative linguistics, study of the stages of formation and development of the Uzbek literary language;

- features of the development of Uzbek language in the 20th and 21st centuries, relationships between related and unrelated languages, history of linguistics, scientific and theoretical views of different linguistic schools, phonology of Uzbek language, lexicology, grammar, onomastics, sociolinguistics, linguopoetics, development of such areas of linguistics as ethnolinguistics, psycholinguistics, cognitive linguistics, pragmatic linguistics and linguistics;

- reveal the history of the formation, stage-by-stage development and patterns of development of the poetic thought of Uzbek people on the basis of studying the origins of the period from the most ancient literary monuments to the modern literary process as an integral artistic system;

- research and promotion of new sources of Uzbek classical literature that have not previously been introduced into scientific circulation, the influence of the process of spiritual and cultural growth that took place in our country in the Middle Ages on fiction, the influence of the works of classic writers and historians of Uzbek language and literature studying the place, the universal significance of the literary heritage of Alisher Navoi, the mastery of using the words of other writers and classical poets, issues of classical literary art;

- develop the most effective methods of teaching Uzbek language and literature at all stages of education, create advanced methods of modern and national philological education, taking into account foreign experience;

- Training of translators of scientific and technical literature, simultaneous translators into Uzbek language and from Uzbek into foreign languages at various international meetings in order to regularly familiarize the people of the world with the achievements of science and culture of Uzbekistan;

- ensuring a worthy place for our Uzbek language in the global information network Internet, creating an electronic systematization of linguistic knowledge and algorithms for linguistic analysis, introducing information and communication technologies into linguistic research based on Uzbek language and creating the leading foreign languages of the world,

translator programs and dictionaries, scientific and methodological developments related to the creation of electronic textbooks.

Conclusion. The sacred duty of each of us is to honor and value our native language, preserve and enhance its rich capabilities and vocabulary, increase its position and prestige as a state language, and be literate.

The state language is our incomparable wealth, our honor. The national language will lead our nation towards development in unity. This encourages people to become more united and preserve national values. Since literate youth are the prospect of the country, the masters of our future, their knowledge and education are important for the state.

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